

EBFMC25-OP-46 · Empowering Primary Care Physicians in Early Diagnose of Heterozygous Familial Hypercholesterolaemia

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Heterozygous familial hypercholesterolaemia (HeFH) is common genetic disorder characterized by high lipid levels, which significantly increases the risk of premature cardiovascular events. Despite its high prevalence of 1 in 250 individuals, lack of general awareness among medical community and difficulties for genetic confirmation for most of cases it remains under-recognized, often treated sub-optimally and diagnosed after early-onset cardiovascular event (Beheshti et al., 2020; Nordestgaard et al., 2013; Vaezi & Amini, 2022). With this collective case summery report, we aimed to emphasis the importance of recognizing HeFH and diagnosing it through the use of clinical criteria.

Case Presentation: The three cases presented in this summary involve males aged ≤ 40 years with significantly elevated total cholesterol (TC) $>9\text{mmol/L}$ and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-c) $>6.5\text{mmol/L}$. They all shared positive family history of hyperlipidemia and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. All cases fulfilled the Dutch Lipid Clinic Network criteria for diagnosing familial hypercholesterolaemia based on their lipid profiles, family history and clinical findings (score of 6: probable FH). One of the patients accepted the referral to cardiologist and genetic testing, while the two others refuse the genetic confirmation of the condition. Despite the difficulty in obtaining genetic diagnoses, clinical suspicion for HeFH was high, and management was initiated based on established HeFH treatment recommendations (Knowles, Rader, & Khoury, 2017). Two of them were prescribed with rosuvastatin 20mg intensified with ezetimibe 10mg. and one case with rosuvastatin 40mg. due to prescription coverage (deGoma et al., 2016).

Results: Among the three cases, only one patient achieved the recommended $\geq 50\%$ reduction in LDL-c levels, decreasing from 7.6 mmol/L to 2.5 mmol/L. The remaining two cases exhibited lower reductions, reaching approximately 45%, one decreasing from 6.6 mmol/L to 3.6 mmol/L and the other from 7.5 mmol/L to 4.1 mmol/L. Despite the implementation of lipid-lowering therapies, none of the patients attained the target LDL-c <1.8 mmol/L, as outlined by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC, 2019) guidelines (European Atherosclerosis Society, 2019; European Society of Cardiology, 2019). These findings suggest that more intensive therapeutic strategies, incorporating combination therapy, may be necessary to enhance LDL-c

reduction aligning with guideline-based targets (Agarwala, Quispe, Goldberg, & Michos, 2021; Grundy et al., 2019).

Conclusion: Despite challenges with genetic testing, clinical diagnosis remains a critical tool in identifying heterozygous familial hypercholesterolemia (HeFH). Physicians must rely on clinical indicators and lipid profiles to facilitate timely intervention through the initiation of lipid-lowering therapies and lifestyle modifications (Representatives of the Global Familial Hypercholesterolemia Community, 2020). Strengthening the role of primary care physicians in recognizing HeFH, optimizing treatment strategies, enhancing long-term therapy adherence and fostering patient involvement through shared decision-making can significantly reduce premature cardiovascular events.

Written informed consent was obtained from the patients.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Heterozygous, familial, hypercholesterolemia, premature, cardiovascular.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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